

Paper 8

CLOUD COMPUTING: IS THE FUTURE NATURAL COMPUTING DOMAIN? AN INTERNATIONAL LOOK

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Abstract

Cloud computing is actually mechanism used for virtualization IT resources software and hardware availability. Cloud computing is helps in using of less computer, hardware including IT Infrastructure delivery. Use of minimum software with utilization of applications is also important features of Cloud Computing and Applications. The development of research activities in Cloud and Higher Education results educational innovations around the world. Thus universities in developed countries are offering programs on Cloud Computing leading to MSc though few are offered BSc- Cloud Computing. However it is important to note that Cloud Computing programs are also offered by the corporate bodies and companies of international level. It is important to note that India is the largest educational system in the world with about 800 Universities and 40000+ institutes of higher education. Even around 5000 institutes are engineering colleges under AICTE. But it is difficult to find a large number of institutes offering Cloud as a Program. Hence we need to build Cloud Computing as a branch of Computing and Information Technology. Naturally in Faculty of Natural Sciences the program may be offered with assistance of other departments in Indian context to see other International Scenario. In this paper several affairs on Cloud Computing is illustrated briefly. Moreover the paper highlighted the emergence on education systems in the areas of Cloud Computing in India as well in the line of western countries. The paper specially highlighted the Bachelors Level of Education leading to Computer Application Track (BCA/MCA).

Keywords

Cloud Computing, Indian Education, Higher Education, International Universities, Cloud Science, India

Introduction

Cloud Computing' is an important and valuable computing and Information Technology tool and mechanism which is mainly deals with Virtualization. With the Cloud Computing any one can go for the Hardware, Software, Network and other IT Infrastructure with remote infrastructure. The concept of Cloud Computing is bigger than virtualization and even from the areas of Grid Computing, Utility Computing and similar platform. As we know that 'Cloud Computing' is a combination of all these systems and mechanisms thus 'Cloud Services' are widely useful and purely user friendly with several scales [1],[5]. This wonderful and massive web scale infrastructure is available from anytime and anywhere. Moreover for this case to case installation of hardware or software is not required. It is also comes with the pay-as-you-go feature and thus helps in increasing popularity. 'Cloud Computing' is a happiness term in the field of IT for specially building of IT infrastructure any kind organization and institutions [2], [3], [6]. Cloud Computing based deployment services may be offered differently and valuable are these three—

- Public Cloud.
- Private Cloud.
- Hybrid Cloud.

Though it is important to note that few cloud computing models are also important in their respective fields and among these few important are include (but not limited to)—

- Community Cloud.
- Shared Private Cloud.
- Dedicated Private Clouds.

Objective

The Main aim and agenda of this paper is includes (but not limited to the following)—

- To learn about the basics of Computer Systems and Information Technology and few emerging areas.
- To know about the Basics of Cloud Computing including its nature or characteristics in brief.
- To know about the basic and emerging types of Cloud Computing & Virtualization that leads the concept of Cloud Computing as a Field of study.
- To learn about the need and role of Cloud Computing and Allied Field as a Program of study in different International Universities.
- To know about the need of Cloud Computing as a domain and rising trend of Cloud as a field of Natural Sciences with respect of Computer Application domains/ degrees.

Cloud Computing: Foundation

Cloud Computing comes with different type of services and among these services few are useful in diverse range [4], [7], [9]. As far as service nature are concerned, all are internet depended thus strong and sophisticated backup is required. More clearly different platform has been used and among these few important are include—

- Platform-as-a-Services/PaaS.
- Software-as-a-Service/SaaS.
- Infrastructure-as-a-Service/IaaS.
- Desktop-as-a-Service/DaaS.
- Security-as-a-Service.

Cloud computing is depends on several tools, techniques and technologies including services and policies for the sustainable development and among these few important are—

- Effective and powerful broadband internet connectivity is required for healthy cloud computing practice [8], [10].
- A big and sophisticated including effective data storage section is required for the healthy and modern cloud computing practice and services [9], [11].
- Healthy information system is important for the cloud computing and similar virtualization practice in all respect.
- Third party dependency is also essential for cloud computing and virtualization practice. Hence solid and secure third party is highly solicited.
- Proper and governmental, organizational policy is highly required for the modern and advanced cloud computing utilization.
- Skilled manpower as well as expertise in the field of cloud computing (including other allied fields) is an important issue.
- Adequate and healthy financial support is required for the designing and development of modern and advanced cloud computing practice and infrastructure.

Cloud Computing towards a Field and Domain: International Context

Cloud Computing is an electronic consortium that depends upon virtualization and play an important role for the creation of centralized systems viz. software, hardware, information systems, application, utilities sharing among the dedicated stakeholders through the dedicated Network and Systems. Healthy and sophisticated broadband connection, centralized service provider, security and privacy, proper and meaningful policies etc are required. The centralized agency any way when avail such services then it is called Public Cloud. Though when services

are arranged in house basis for the organization and uses only for the connected organizations or sister organizations that is called Private Cloud [6], [12], [15]. Moreover the combination of both the computing model viz. Public Cloud Computing and Private Cloud Computing is treated as Hybrid Cloud.

Cloud computing is also introduced in business environment where users can interact directly with the virtualized resources and save the cost for the consumers. Cloud computing provides the scalable and efficient means for managing IT resources within organizations and institutions. An organization used private clouds within the organization for the prevention and also loss of data. Cloud computing has numerous deployment models and here various platform are important and valuable viz. SaaS, PaaS, IaaS are the three models for cloud computing [7], [13], [14].

Cloud Computing a Natural Science Field: Rising Trend in India

Computing and Information Sciences (*which includes Computer Science, Computer Applications, Information Technology, Information Science, Informatics*) is emerging rapidly. These are part of several sub fields within Information Technology viz. Networking Technologies, Database Technologies, Communication Technology, Multimedia Technology, Web Technology etc and all these in recent past become a field and study area [7], [15].

Moreover there are many new interdisciplinary and broad subjects have been developed in recent past and also many new smaller and skill based areas and subjects. And among these few important are include (*but not limited to*) the Big Data Science, Big Data Technologies, Human Computer Interaction, Usability Engineering, User Experience Designing, Cloud Computing, Virtualization, Internet of Things (IoT) etc. And internationally these fields become a full-fledged subject in many context

Indian Higher Education is rapidly growing and this is the world largest knowledge provider i.e. 40000+ Higher Educational Institutes. Though in terms of degree awarding body there are about 800+ universities pan India basis with different types such as Central Universities, Private Universities, Deemed Universities, State Universities etc. Institute of National Importance (INI) is another kind of institutions (*a basic overview on this areas has been provided in Table: 1*). Information Technology academics in India basically concentrated on software and programming technologies and importantly a very limited institute offers Data and Networking Technology foci. Though internationally there is a healthy focus on the allied technologies viz. Networking Technologies, Database Technologies, Communication Technology, Multimedia Technology, Web Technology in IT program [8], [16].

Table: 1-Higher Educational Institutes (HEIs) at a glance

Universities	In Numbers	Location
Institute of National Importance (INI) Such as IITs NITs IIITs IIMs IEST SPA AIIMS etc	93	Pan India with 28 States and UT
Central Universities	47	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Universities	370	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Private Universities	290	Except some states and UT
Deemed Universities	123	Except some states and UT

In recent past many international universities have been started the Cloud Computing programs in a different way. Among the International Universities and programs, few important are include but not limited to the following—

- University of Newcastle (MSc Cloud Computing)
- University of Essex (MSc Cloud Computing)
- University of Leicester (MSc Cloud Computing)
- National University of Ireland (MSc Cloud Computing)
- Dublin City University (MSc Computing—*Cloud Computing*)
- Nottingham Trent University (MSc Cloud & Enterprise Computing)
- Middlesex University, Dubai (MSc Cloud Computing)

Though, in India also Cloud Computing and allied areas (Networking, Virtualization) have been mapped in the private universities in this study with special reference to the Computer Application Program. And it has been studied that the areas are being offered in Engineering, Technology, Science, Management, Computer Application etc with the focus viz.—

- Full-fledged Degree
- Major/ Honors
- Specializations

As far as the present study is concerned it has been noted that among the 279 private universities 10 have started program on Cloud Computing and it has become a natural computing and science track (i.e. Computer Application). Though among the universities Srinivas University, Karnataka play a good role in terms of producing good number of programs—

- BCA (Data Analytics & Cloud Computing)
- Integrated MCA (4 Year) & Trimester Based (10+2 Any)- (*With Specialization Networking & Cloud Computing with 2nd Big Data*)
- 2 Year MCA (Related Degree)- *With Specialization Networking & Cloud Computing with 2nd Specialization Big Data*

The details of such programs and universities have been provided in Table: 2 for more reference including the eligibility criteria where opened to diverse background [6].

Table: 2-Cloud Computing as a Natural Science Domain

Sl. No.	Private Universities in India offering Cloud and Allied Technologies Programs (Computer Application Track)	
	Universities	Programs
1	Assam Down Town University	BCA/MCA Integrated- Cloud Technology & Information Security / BCA-Cloud Technology & Information Security
2	The Assam Kaziranga University	BCA-MCA Integrated (Cloud Technology & Information Security)/ MCA (Cloud Technology)
3	Srinivas University	BCA (Data Analytics & Cloud Computing) Integrated MCA (4 Year) & Trimester Based (10+2 Any)- (<i>With Specialization Networking & Cloud Computing with 2nd Big Data</i>) 2 Year MCA (Related Degree)- <i>With Specialization Networking & Cloud Computing with 2nd Specialization Big Data</i>
4	Mandsaur University	BCA (Cloud Computing)
5	Ajeenkya D.Y. Patil University	BCA (Cloud Technology & Information Security) BCA (Mobile Application & Cloud Technology)
6	Sandip University	BCA- (Cloud Technology & Information Security)
7	Chandigarh University	BCA (Information Security & Cloud Computing)
8	RayatBahra University	MCA- Networking (Any Degree)
9	Poornima University	BCA (Mobile Application & Information Security-10+2 with Science/ BCA (IT Infrastructure Management & Cloud Technology-10+2 Any)

10	Sikkim Manipal University	BCA (Cloud Technology & Information Security)
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Suggestions and Future Possibilities

India holds a large number of universities and institutions including a good number of Engineering Colleges offering Technological Degrees leading to BTech/BE/MTech/ME. Hence it is possible to include this specialization in the traditional Computing track leading to Computer Science/ Computer Science and Engineering/ Information Technology as a Major/ Specialization or even Full-Fledged Degree on the area is possible viz. BTech/MTech-Cloud Computing. Though based the justification of the program in future it may also be offered as a Specialization. Similarly the areas may also offered with BSc/MSc track and here also we can start the program under the banner of Computer Science/ Computer Science and Engineering/ Information Technology.

Naturally in Computer Application Track also this educational strategy may be increased and specifically in Masters Degree. Though, as far as interdisciplinary programs are concerned it may be started (in future if such field gets started) in different interdisciplinary areas viz.

- Information Science
- Informatics
- Information Management
- Information Systems
- Information Science and Technology etc

Thus there are huge potentialities waiting for the future to promote Cloud Computing as a Natural Computing domain.

Conclusion

Research is the driving force for the development and there are many ways to improve the education systems. The specialized areas within Information Technology are include Big Data Science, Big Data Technologies, Human Computer Interaction, Usability Engineering, User Experience Designing, Cloud Computing, Virtualization, Internet of Things (IoT) etc and in all these areas due to job potentialities specialization either started or may be offered. As far as India is concerned these areas and obviously Cloud Computing may be started as an academic program more boarder context. Though it is important to note that already this areas have been emerged and available as a program of study as a Basic and Natural Science and more can be utilized with this effect. The program leading to MPhil/PhD in Computer Science/Computer Application/ Information Technology/ may have specialization in Cloud Computing and Allied areas viz. IT Infrastructure Management, Virtualization etc. Here notable would be the

introduction of the rigorous coursework in Cloud Computing and Allied areas including research work at the MPhil/PhDs.

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